

Our experiments have shown that the oxidation of ferroin by dichromate occurs instantaneously only in a medium which is at least 5 *M* in sulphuric acid or hydrochloric acid or 7 *M* in phosphoric acid, whereas the titration of hexacyanoferrate(II) is possible even at lower acidities. A detailed investigation of this anomaly has shown that at lower acidities, the ferroin-dichromate reaction is (1) induced by hexacyanoferrate(II), (2) catalysed by hexacyanoferrate(III), and (3) unaffected by chromium(III). Thus this is a case of induction and autocatalysis. Separate experiments have shown that the reduction of ferroin by hexacyanoferrate(II) is almost instantaneous under the conditions of titration.

Dichrometric titration of hydroquinone: The titration of hydroquinone with potassium dichromate using ferroin as indicator can also be carried out in 2-4 *M* hydrochloric acid or 4.5-7.0 *M* phosphoric acid medium, if the titration mixture contains 0.5 ml of 1% potassium hexacyanoferrate(III) or 5-10 ml of 0.1*N* uranium(VI). The titration is also possible in a medium of 8-10*M* phosphoric acid, provided it is carried out slowly in the vicinity of the end point, waiting for about 10-15 sec. after each addition.

Titration of 0.01 *N* solutions of hydroquinone with 0.01 *N* dichromate solution are also satisfactory; in this case, an indicator correction of 0.1 ml of 0.01 *N* dichromate has to be applied.

The titrations of dichromate with hydroquinone also can be carried out under the same conditions of direct titrations. In this connection, it may be mentioned that the procedure now developed by the authors is advantageous over those reported by Kolthoff² (potentiometric titration) and Simon and Zyka³ (40°-50° and diphenylamine as indicator).

The possibility of the titration of hydroquinone with dichromate at lower acid concentrations and the role of hexacyanoferrate(III), uranium (VI) and iron(III) in this titration are similar to those recently reported by us in the dichrometric titration of hydroquinone using triphenylmethane dyes as redox indicators⁴.

Vanadometric titration of hydroquinone: The vanadometric titration of hydroquinone, employing ferroin as indicator, gives very good results when carried out in 7-10 *M* phosphoric acid medium also, whereas in hydrochloric acid medium, the end points are fleeting and the colour change at the end point is not at all satisfactory.

The reverse titration, i. e., titration of vanadate with hydroquinone employing ferroin as indicator, can be performed under the same conditions of the direct titration and is advantageous over those of Kolthoff² and Simon and Zyka³.

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References

1. K. SOMEYA., *Z. anorg. Chem.*, 1926, **159**, 758.
2. I. M. KOLTHOFF., *Rec. Trav. Chim.*, 1926, **45**, 745.
3. V. SIMON and J. ZYKA., *Chem. Listy*, 1955, **49**, 1646.
4. N. V. RAO and V. V. S. E. DUTT., *Z. Anal. Chem.*, 1971, **254**, 110.

Fluoroniobates (V) of Organic Base Cations

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A large number of fluoroniobates of various metals are known¹⁻³. Recently a series of compounds containing protonated hydrazine and ethylenediamine have been reported by Buslaev and others⁴. The present work deals with the isolation of fluoroniobates of various other organic base cations.

Experimental

Methods of Analysis: The compounds were decomposed by (1 : 1) H₂SO₄ and niobium was then gravimetrically estimated as niobium pentoxide from its cupferronate precipitate. Fluorine was estimated gravimetrically as lead chlorofluoride after separating niobium as hydrated niobium pentoxide. Nitrogen was estimated by Dumas method.

The analytical results are reported in Table I.

1. Oxotetrafluoroniobates, BH(NbOF₄), where B = Pyridine, α-, β-, δ-picolines and quinoline : Nb₂O₅ was dissolved in minimum volume of 40% hydrofluoric acid by heating on a water bath. Calculated amount of organic base (Nb₂O₅ : organic base = 1 : 2) was acidified with 10% HF and then added dropwise to the above solution. The resulting mixture was evaporated on a water bath to crystallisation. The crystals were filtered, pressed between filter papers and dried to constant weight in vacuum over H₂SO₄ and KOH.

2. Guanidinium oxopentafluoroniobate, CH₅N₃H₂(NbOF₅) : The compound was prepared through the above procedure from Nb₂O₅ and guanidine carbonate in 2 : 1 ratio.

3. *o*-phenanthroline oxotetrafluoroniobate, C₁₂H₈N₂H(NbOF₄) : By the above procedure the compound was obtained as a white crystalline precipitate on mixing the two components in the cold condition in 1 : 1 ratio.

4. Nitron hexafluoroniobate, C₂₀H₁₆N₄H(NbF₆) : Dark brown crystals of the compound was obtained on dropwise addition of glacial acetic acid solution of nitron (Nb₂O₅ : Nitron = 1 : 1) to a hot solution of fluoroniobate prepared as before. The resulting mixture was partially evaporated on a water bath and the crystals obtained were filtered and dried as above.

5. α, α' -dipyridyl hexafluoroniobate, C₁₀H₈N₂H₂(NbF₆)₂ : The compound was prepared as the above oxotetrafluoroniobates from Nb₂O₅ : α, α' -dipyridyl in 1 : 1 ratio.

TABLE 1—ANALYTICAL DATA OF FLUORONILOBATES OF ORGANIC BASE CATIONS

Compound	Found			Required		
	%N	%Nb	%F	%N	%Nb	%F
(Pyridine H) (NbOF ₄), C ₅ H ₅ NH(NbOF ₄)	5.41	34.9	29.0	5.28	35.1	28.7
(α -picoline H) (NbOF ₄), C ₆ H ₇ NH(NbOF ₄)	4.90	33.3	26.8	5.03	33.3	27.2
(β -picoline H) (NbOF ₄), C ₆ H ₇ NH(NbOF ₄)	4.89	33.4	27.4	5.03	33.3	27.2
(δ -picoline H) (NbOF ₄), C ₆ H ₇ NH(NbOF ₄)	4.72	33.6	27.1	5.03	33.3	27.2
(Quinoline H) (NbOF ₄), C ₉ H ₇ NH(NbOF ₄)	4.63	39.9	24.4	4.44	29.5	24.1
(<i>o</i> -phenanthroline H) (NbOF ₄), C ₁₂ H ₈ N ₂ H(NbOF ₄)	7.29	25.6	20.7	7.65	25.4	20.8
(Guanidine H ₂) (NbOF ₅), CH ₅ N ₃ H ₂ (NbOF ₅)	16.4	35.7	36.4	15.9	35.1	35.9
(Nitron H) (NbF ₆), C ₂₀ H ₁₆ N ₄ H(NbF ₆)	10.8	17.8	21.7	10.8	17.9	21.9
(α, α' -dipyridyl H ₂) (NbF ₆) ₂ , C ₁₀ H ₈ N ₂ H ₂ (NbF ₆) ₂	—	32.6	39.3	—	32.5	39.9

The compounds containing NbOF₄ group are well-crystalline, white, nonhygroscopic solids. The salts obtained from pyridine, quinoline and orthophenanthroline are highly soluble in water, whilst the solubility of picoline compound decreases according to the series $\alpha > \beta > \delta$. All the compounds are insoluble in most of the common organic solvents. Guanidinium and dipyridyl salts are highly soluble in water, whereas nitron salt is sparingly soluble and hydrolyses on boiling. The nitron salt is soluble in acetic acid, alcohol, acetone, dioxan, etc.

It has been found that all the compounds except those of nitron and dipyridyl decompose without melting. The melting point of the nitron compound is 194° and that of dipyridyl compound above 300°.

Thermogravimetric studies: All the fluoroniobates are studied by thermogravimetry in a manually operated thermobalance at the heating rate of 2°C/min. Only in the case of dipyridyl compound an intermediate compound is formed in the temperature range 260°–350°, but it is so unstable that it cannot be isolated by isothermal heating of the compound at 240° to 250°. Maximum decomposition of the compounds takes place in the range 200°–300°, and near about 500° Nb₂O₅ is produced from them.

Infrared spectral studies: All the compounds have been studied through infrared spectroscopy in the region 700 cm⁻¹ to 4000 cm⁻¹. Pyridine, α -, β -, δ -picolines, quinoline and orthophenanthroline compounds show broad strong absorption bands due to Nb-O⁵ in the regions 780 cm⁻¹–845 cm⁻¹, 785 cm⁻¹–839 cm⁻¹, 780 cm⁻¹–800 cm⁻¹, 798 cm⁻¹–826 cm⁻¹, 790 cm⁻¹–820 cm⁻¹ and 787 cm⁻¹–810 cm⁻¹ respectively. Besides, known expected bands corresponding to these compounds are also found to occur. The above band due to Nb-O is absent in the nitron salt, but the dipyridyl compound shows a strong band in the region 797 cm⁻¹–835 cm⁻¹, which is also found in dipyridyl itself.

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References

1. J.N. FRIEND, A Text Book of Inorganic Chemistry, Charles Griffin and Company Limited, London, 1929, Vol VI, Part III, p. 143.
2. J.W. MELLOR, A Comprehensive Treatise on Inorganic and Theoretical Chemistry, Longmans, London, 1960, Vol IX, p. 870.

3. J. H. SIMONS, Fluorine Chemistry, Academic Press, Inc., New York, 1964, Vol V, p. 47.
4. YU. A. BUSLAEV, E. G. II' in, S.V. Bainova, Izv Akad Nauk SSSR, *Neorg Mater*, 1971, 7, 184.
5. VU, A. BUSLAEV, YU. YA. KHARITONOV AND S. M. SINITSYNA, *Zh. Neorg. Khim.*, 1965, 10, 533.

Kinetics of Cr (VI) Oxidation of 1-and 2-Acetylnaphthalene

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ALTHOUGH chromic acid has been used as a versatile oxidant for the last two decades¹, the kinetics and mechanism of the oxidation of ketones, is of very recent origin. Best and Littler² have studied the kinetics of the oxidation of cyclohexanone by chromic acid. Rocek and Reihl³ have reported that aliphatic ketones are oxidised via their enol form. Bakore and coworkers⁴ have studied the kinetics and mechanism of chromic acid oxidation of some aliphatic ketones. Very recently we have reported the kinetics and mechanism of oxidation of some aromatic ketones⁵. The present paper deals with the kinetics of the oxidation of some ketones of the naphthalene series.

The ketones, 1-acetylnaphthalene and 2-acetylnaphthalene were prepared and purified according to the literature method⁶. The kinetics of these oxidations were studied in 90% HOAC—10% H₂O (vol/vol) in the presence of perchloric acid and at constant ionic strength. The method of rate measurement is similar to our previous method⁵.

The rate of disappearance of Cr (VI) followed first order rate law, but the values of rate constants decreased with increase in [Cr (VI)]. The reaction is also first order with respect to the [Ketone]. Under the conditions of constant ionic strength the first order rate constant k_1 is proportional to [H⁺].

The reaction has been studied in various acetic acid-water binary mixtures. Increase in the proportion of acetic acid in the reaction mixture increases the rate of oxidation. This is probably due to the lowering of dielectric constant of the medium, which favours reactions involving protonation⁷. The rate of the reaction decreases in the presence of added Mn (II) ions. The same retardation of reaction rate has been